

Anaerobic Structural Adhesives

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ABSTRACT

New anaerobic structural adhesives have been developed especially for metal and plastics bondings and their performance was investigated. The characteristic feature of the adhesives is that they contain methacrylic-modified rubber as one of their components. The adhesives cure rapidly at room temperature under the anaerobic conditions. Containing the above mentioned modified rubber, the adhesives have rapid cure rate, good fatigue resistance and impact resistance. These properties were also supported by the results of acoustic emission measurements. It was also observed that the adhesives have good low and high temperature properties.

INTRODUCTION

Recently many kinds of adhesives have been developed as assembly tools of composite materials.⁽¹⁾ In general the bonding with adhesives saves energy compared with conventional mechanical fastening methods. It also has an advantage of dispersing stress at joints. For structural adhesives high performance of strength and durability are required. In order to improve the performance of the adhesives, especially for fatigue or impact resistance the authors have been developed anaerobic structural adhesives which contain methacrylic-modified rubber as one of their components. The adhesives can be cured at room temperature under the anaerobic conditions. The reaction can be accelerated by redox-type catalysts. In this paper, the almost all experimental results were obtained when steel and aluminum specimens were used as adherends. The adhesives may be suitable for other materials such as glass, FRP, nylon and so on.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of Adhesives

The anaerobic adhesives are basically comprised of two components, a modified rubber and vinyl monomers. As a rubber component, butadiene rubber, styrene-butadiene rubber, nitrile-butadiene rubber can be used. The adhesives may also contain a small amount of peroxide as an initiator. Tertiary amins were used as primers to accelerate the curing rate of the adhesives.

A typical composition of the adhesives is given in Table 1. This adhesive is referred to "Adhesive-A" in this paper. Fig.1 shows the Chemical reaction of

modification of rubber with methacrylic acid in the presence of tert-Butyl hypochlorite.^{(2),(3),(4)} For the Adhesive-A, a radial block styrene-butadiene copolymer, Solprene 414 (Philips Chemical Comp.) was used. The prepared rubber had a methacryloyloxy group as a pendant. The IR and ¹³C-NMR analysis verified the modification of the rubber. Fig.2 shows the IR spectra of the original and modified Solprene 414. The new absorptions at 1160cm⁻¹ and 1720cm⁻¹ were seen in the spectrum of the modified rubber. These absorptions were assigned to the stretching vibration of C-O and C=O of methacryloyloxy group respectively.

Sample Preparation for strength Measurement

For tensile shear strength measurements, single-lap jointed specimens of steel plates (100 x 25 x 1.6mm) or aluminum plates (100 x 25 x 3) were made. The plates were polished with #240 sandpaper and degreased in acetone. The plates were bonded by applying a thin primer to half of the test specimens and the adhesive to the remaining plates. The parts were mated using only contact pressure to give a 12.5mm overlap. Rod-type specimens of aluminum were applied for another measurements. The strength of jointed specimens were measured after more than 24-hour aging at room temperature.

Measurement Method

Shear Tensile Strength. Instron type tensile testing machine was employed. The cross head speed of 5mm/min was used.

Fatigue Experiments. The experiment were carried out by adding cyclic load on single-lap jointed steel specimens with using a electro-hydraulically operated testing machine, SERVO-PAC-10 (Saginomiya Comp.). The Fig.3-a shows a rough sketch of the test. The experimental conditions are given in Fig.3-b.

Impact Resistance. The retained shear strength of single-lap jointed steel specimens were measured after samples were damaged with impact loading by dropping a steel-ball (1.8kg weight) from 60cm height.

Acoustic Emission Measurement. The 1032 D Measurement System (DUNEGAN/ENDEVCO.) was used for the measurements of acoustic emission. The monitoring of A.E. was carried out during single-lap jointed specimens were bending as shown in Fig.4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shear strength

Fig.5 shows the typical development of shear strength when bonding steel or aluminum plates with the Adhesive-A. As the figure indicates, there was a short induction period of several minutes during which polimerization began. After approximately 5-10 minutes, the bond strength was about 10-20kg/cm² and jointed samples were handleable. The strength reached its maximum value in 24 hours at room temperature. The final shear strength were about 260kg/cm² and 160kg/cm² for steel and aluminum plates respectively. This results would not mean that the bond strength for aluminum is weaker than that of steel. The values in Fig.5 were obtained when the measurements were performed with single-lap jointed plates.. Aluminum plates are weaker than steel ones and begin to deform at a much lower applied stress and the non-uniform stress distribution causes the bond to fail at the lower stress. As a matter of fact, shear strength higher than 300kg/cm² was obtained with aluminum rod-type specimens.

Fatigue Experiments

The results of the repeated cycles of loading to failure are shown in Table 2. As references, commercially available acryle-type adhesive and epoxy-type one were tested. Samples were prepared according to the recomended methods by the producers. The result showed that Adhesive-A had good faigue-resistance compared with the other type adhesives.

Impact Resistance

The absolute values of the retained strength versus repeated times of dropping ball are shown in Fig.6. The specimens jointed with an epoxy-type

adhesive were destroyed in the first dropping test.

Acoustic Emission Measurement

Fig.7 shows the history of load and monitored acoustic emission events rate (events per second) of the specimen jointed with the Adhesive-A. The result with an epoxy-type is also shown in Fig.8. In the case of an epoxy, the first A.E. event was monitored at the load of about 20-30kg. In contrast, in the case of the Adhesive-A, the initial A.E. event was monitored at 150 kg. Those results mean that the internal destruction of the epoxy-type adhesive began shortly after the joint was bended. In contrast, for the Adhesive-A, it has enough flexibility owing to modified rubber component, and acoustic emissions were not recorded until the bending load reached the maximum value. The results of A.E. experiments supported the good fatigue and impact resistance of the Adhesive-A.

It was found that the degree of modification of polymers have remarkable effects on compatibility of the adhesive solution and especially on cure rate and high-temperature properties of the adhesives. Fig.9 and Fig.10 show the cure rate and strength at elevated temperatures of adhesives with varying the degree of modification (number of MAA pendant per molecular weight of rubber). Cure rate of non-modified adhesive was fairly slow and resulting shear strength was not adequate.

CONCLUSION

New anaerobic structural adhesives containing methacrylic-modified rubber as one of its components were developed. Owing to the modified rubber, the adhesives have flexibility and good fatigue and impact resistance. Adding to those performances, the adhesives can be cured rapidly at room temperature.

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REFERENCES

1. Martin Hauser and John T. Loft, "Anaerobic and Modified Acrylic Adhesives": Adhesives Age (December, 1980) p21
2. Carl F. Irwin and G. F. Hennion, "Chlorination of Olefins in Reactive Solvents with t-Butyl Hypochlorite": J.Am.Chem.Soc. 63 (1941) p858
3. D. E. Winkler and C. W. Hearne, "Reactions of t-Butyl Hypochlorite": J.Org.Chem. 25 (1960) p1835
4. Honda T., Japanese an Examined Patent Application No. 84307/80

Table 1 Typical Composition

ADHESIVE-A	
MAA-modified *	20 wt%
Solprene 414	
Methacrylic Acid	30
Methylmethacrylate	50
Cumenhydroperoxide	1
Parabenzoquinone	0,003
* 1/500 MAA-modified	

Fig.1 Chemical Reaction of modification of rubber

Fig.2 IR spectra of original and modified radial block styrene-butadiene copolymers.

Fig.3-a Fatigue test

Fig.3-b Experimental conditions of fatigue test

Fig.4 Diagram of the acoustic emission measurement

Fig.5 Development of shear strength with time

Table 2 Loading cycles to failure

Dynamic Load	Adhesive -A	Adhesive (acryl type)	Adhesive (epoxy type)
100 kg	$> 10^6$ cycles	$1 \sim 4 \times 10^5$	$1 \sim 2 \times 10^5$
150	$> 10^6$	$5 \sim 10 \times 10^4$	$4 \sim 8 \times 10^4$
200	2×10^5	5×10^4	4×10^4

Fig.6 Retained Strength vs. drop ball times

Fig.7 Acoustic Emission events of the single-lap specimen bonded with the Adhesive-A

Fig.8 Acoustic Emission events of the single-lap specimen bonded with an epoxy-type adhesive

Fig.9 Effect of the modification on the development of shear strength

Fig.10 Effect of the modification on the shear strength at elevated temperature

